

A multifield continuum model for the description of the response of microporous/microcracked composite materials

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Abstract

The description of the mechanical behavior of composite materials is an open challenge in engineering. The focus of this work is on micro-cracked/microporous composites, made of stiff grains embedded in a cracked or porous deformable matrix. Grains interact between each other and with cracks or pores localized at the interfaces, which reduce the contact area between grains. Pores' interaction is also taken into account. We apply a two-scale modeling strategy based on a discrete to scale-dependent (non-classical) continuum equivalence procedure. The constitutive relationships of the resulting microcontinuum, identified by requiring equivalence, in terms of virtual work, between discrete and continuum non-local descriptions of the reference material, take directly into account the material internal structure, and in particular material internal lengths. Field and boundary conditions of the equivalent continuum are also derived based on work equivalence between internal and external actions. The response of the obtained one-dimensional equivalent model and of a finite element model of a bar with pores are compared, showing a very good match between each other in a wide range of pore densities.

Keywords:

continua with microstructure, non-local continua, microcracked composites, composite materials, multiscale modelling

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1. Introduction

Many materials at the cutting edge of material technology, with exceptional performances in terms of low weight and high strength, appropriate to demanding applications such as aircrafts, spacecrafts, pressure vessels, offshore structures, wind turbines blades, reinforcements of structures damaged by earthquakes, combine dissimilar constituents. These heterogeneous, and often discontinuous materials exhibit a mechanical behavior that is not simply the sum of the properties of the constituents: they present complex features depending on properties and interactions at the nano, micro or meso-scale, which cannot be described by homogeneous models of continuum. Failure mechanisms (damage, plasticity, fracture, instability, etc.) and wave propagation happen to be governed by their internal structure (microstructure). The design of such materials requires the ability to formulate mechanical models describing their macroscopic behaviour. These models must take into account the internal structure, size, shape, and spatial distribution of the microstructural constituents, which can span several orders of magnitude in length, starting from the submicron scale to millimeter scale or even larger scales.

The first obstacle with the mechanical modeling of complex materials is the definition of constitutive laws which adequately take into account microscopic features, avoiding a direct Lagrangian modeling of the microstructure, which can result in cumbersome problems with many degrees of freedom [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. To deal with a multiscale phenomenology, several homogenization or coarse-graining methods can be found in literature [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13]. Nevertheless, most of the classical homogenized models are standard (Grade 1) continua that exhibit two major drawbacks. The first is the absence of internal-length scale parameters. As a consequence, models cannot predict the effect of the size of heterogeneities since they only account for the shape of internal phases and, in some cases, for the morphology of the heterophase distribution [14, 15]. Moreover, the classical homogenized models generally assume the local macroscopic uniformity of the stress-strain fields, which is likely to be inappropriate in critical regions of high gradients, i.e., in the vicinity of a macroscopic discontinuity, such as a joint or a hole, or close to the point of application of a localized load [16, 17, 18, 19].

Several models were proposed to overcome difficulties related to the adoption of classical local models, generally due to the inability of retaining memory of the internal-length scale [20, 21]. This was done by introducing non-

simple explicit or implicit non-local models [22, 23, 13, 24], which allow one to avoid ill-posed field-equations and mesh dependence in the numerical solutions. Within this framework, various approaches have been presented concerning higher-order models or second gradient models (Mindlin-Toupin type) [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31], or also micromorphic continua [23], and in particular, micropolar continua [32], which can be considered non-local models of implicit type [33, 34, 14, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41]. We particularly focus on multiscale approaches and, among the latter kind of non-local models, continua with affine microstructure [42] or continua with configurational forces [43], as [44, 45, 46]. In all non local models, there are internal length scales, and the microstructure is revealed by the dispersive character of propagating waves, which results in a frequency-dependent wave propagation speed and consequent space and time distortion of a non-monochromatic propagating disturbance [20, 21, 45, 47, 48, 49, 50].

Concerning multiscale approaches, in structural mechanics and material engineering, it generally suffices to link only two scales: a fine scale, conventionally defined microscopic, and a gross continuum scale referred to as macroscopic. In this work, we generalize the mentioned multiscale approach first presented in [51, 45] and further developed in [46, 48] to grossly describe the mechanical behavior of composite media made of stiff and strong fibers or grains embedded in a deformable matrix, which, due to manufacturing defects, lack of cohesion or functional needs, present distributed microflaws or pores. Our approach relates macroscopic deformations of continua to changes in positions and other parameters describing the material microstructure of specific periodic lattice models. It is based on the molecular/energetic theory of elasticity originally formulated by Voigt in [52, 53], which was described in tensorial form in [54], and further developed to also account for nonlinear and nonlocal effects in research on continuum micromechanics [55, 22] and in atomistic-continuum models for complex materials [56, 57, 58, 11].

The energy equivalent continuous models derived in this way present additional degrees of freedom and can be termed as multifield continuous models [42, 23, 59], which allow to retain memory of the fine organization of the material. For such continua, the basic starting point is to consider the generic material module as a system and to introduce information on the material microstructure at the geometrical level of the body description [42]. The material module is then characterized by suitable field descriptors of the microstructural morphology, which are associated with interactions that satisfy suitable balance equations and pose non-trivial constitutive problems.

The multiscale approach adopted here starts from a kinematical description of the material at the level of the microstructure (fibers or grains, matrix and microcracks). Then, it applies a virtual work equivalence between micro and macro to derive the macroscopic constitutive description. The multifield continuum is characterized by three kinematical descriptors: the standard displacement field, the microtation, plus an additional microdisplacement field. The two non-standard fields, respectively, account for the presence of microcracks and fibers/grains. The role of such additional fields is to effectively spread the microscopic heterogeneities (microcracks and fibers/grains) in the macroscopic continuum, allowing at the same time the introduction of material length scales (the size of the heterogeneities with respect to the leading dimension of the macroscopic system), besides the fiber/grain and microcrack densities and aspect ratios, which can also be present in the conventional Cauchy continuum. The macromodel adopted is an implicit non-local continuum whose strain measures that are the first gradient of macro and micro displacements as well as the second gradient of microdisplacements. The reason for this choice is that we aim at a more refined description of the microdisplacement, which includes nonlocal effects, also accounting for non-contact actions between slits and particle/slits.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a short description of the multifield continuum model and of its discrete counterpart, while Section 3 and 4 describe, respectively, how the constitutive relationships and the balance equations of the multifield continuum are derived. Section 5 presents an application to a one-dimensional model and, finally, Section 6 a comparison with finite-element models. Conclusive comments are reported in Section 7.

2. The multi-field continuum model

The reference material considered in this paper is a fibre-reinforced microcracked composite, that is, for instance, a ductile polymer composite with long carbon fibres or grains, or, also, a masonry-like material with stone/bricks embedded in a mortar matrix, with a distribution of slit microcavities in the matrix. At the microscopic level such material is described by interacting lattice systems. One lattice, made of rigid particles of given shape, represents the fibres/grains in the matrix, and the other lattice, made of interacting slits of arbitrary shape with a predominant dimension, represents the microcracks. In general, the lattice connections can be described

through non-linear elastic bonds [60], although here we focus on linear elastic bonds. The interaction between the two lattices is also considered.

Assuming that the material microstructure is periodic, or at least statistically homogeneous, a representative volume element, here referred to as module, can be defined as in Figure 1. In this paper, the procedure governing the scale transition between the micromodel and the macromodel is based on the Voigt's approach, which includes a mechanistic-energetic homogenization exploiting an enrichment of the kinematics of the discrete system [38, 54]. Generalization of this approach to different lattice systems by endowing their particles with structure, such as extension or properties representing whatever kind of material microstructure (i.e. defects, voids, rigid inclusions, etc.), leads to the identification of constitutive relations and definition of balance equations for size-dependent multi-field continua, within the general framework of the micro-macro virtual work equivalence.

Figure 1: Example of module with hexagonal symmetry with particles and slits: a) interactions between particles b) interactions slits/slits c) interactions particle/slit.

According to Capriz [42], a continuum with microstructure is a mathematical model of material points endowed with a microscopic order preserving the classical scheme of the continuum description. Each material point P is identified with its geometrical position vector $\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{E}$, \mathcal{E} being the three-dimensional Euclidean space, and ν parameters Ξ_α ($\alpha = 1, 2, \dots, \nu$), representing the inner structure. These so-called order parameters belong to an appropriate manifold, \mathcal{M} , of given dimension. A complete placement for P is: $P(\mathbf{p}, \Xi_\alpha)$ ($\alpha = 1, \dots, \nu$). The parameters, and, depending on the case, their gradients, are included in the internal power formula as primal variables, and define the grade of the micromodel. They can be of any nature, not necessarily kinematic, that is, this scheme is compatible with the description

of a material point endowed with physical or geometrical properties, such as mass, porosity, extension, orientation, electric or magnetic field, etc.

The discrete model adopted for the fine-detailed description of the reference composite material is made of structured molecules representing the internal phases of the material: the fibres or grains, described as rigid particles, and the flaws, that are slits of arbitrary shape with a predominant dimension. The slits are assumed to be open, and their number is given, that is, the material has no fracture properties. To avoid the arising of tip effects, we assume that slits have blunt edges. The particles interact in pairs through forces and couples while the slits interact through forces. Particles and slits also interact with each other by means of forces. The slits must be considered as devices that transmit to the matrix additional forces due to the presence of defects. In this sense, they represent the microcracks/pores. Their stiffness depends on the surrounding elastic field. The whole problem is set within the framework of the linearized theory of infinitesimal displacements and rotations, so that displacements and rotations act as velocities and angular velocities occurring in an infinitesimal unit time step.

In the case studied here, the list of kinematical descriptors which define a complete placement for the body point X will be:

$$\mathbf{U}(X) = \{\mathbf{p}(X), \mathbf{c}(X)\} \quad (1)$$

where the vector \mathbf{p} is the standard placement (macrofield), and the vector \mathbf{c} is a non-standard vector field (microfield). This additional kinematic field accounts for the smeared displacement jump (crack opening displacement) due to the presence of distributed microcracks in the body. For a microcracked composite, different choices may be made for the microfield. One possible choice for the microfield adopted by one of the authors et al. [45, 51, 48] is the relative displacement field (microfield) accounting for the crack-opening displacement in a smeared sense. This corresponds to introducing an additional strain measure of grade zero. In the present work, a different choice is adopted: the additional displacement field is defined as the difference between the displacements \mathbf{u}_d of a couple of slits, which will prove to be very effective when comparing the model response to that obtained from finite element models. The total displacement \mathbf{u}_t will be obtained as the sum of the macro and microdisplacement: $\mathbf{u}_t = \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{u}_d$.

Figure 2: Sketch of grains, slits and their kinematical descriptors.

3. The microcracked continuum equivalent to a discrete lattice: derivation of constitutive relations

Assume that \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} are two rigid particles embedded in a microcracked matrix (Figure 2). The kinematical lattice descriptors of a given particle $A(B)$ are the displacement vector \mathbf{u}^a (\mathbf{u}^b) of its centre A (B) and the skew-symmetric rotation tensor \mathbf{W}^a (\mathbf{W}^b) of the particle. The displacement of a point at position P^a belonging to a particle \mathcal{A} is written as:

$$\mathbf{u}_p^a = \mathbf{u}^a + \mathbf{W}^a(P^a - A). \quad (2)$$

Assuming that particles \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} interact through the point $P \equiv P^a \equiv P^b$, the strain measures of the discrete assembly are: (a) the relative displacement between the two particles at their contact points P^a and P^b , represented by vector

$$\mathbf{u}_p = \mathbf{u}_p^a - \mathbf{u}_p^b = \mathbf{u}^a - \mathbf{u}^b + \mathbf{W}^a(P - A) - \mathbf{W}^b(P - B) \quad (3)$$

(b) the relative rotation between the two particles \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} :

$$\mathbf{W}_p = \mathbf{W}^a - \mathbf{W}^b. \quad (4)$$

The discrete assembly can undergo deformations also due to the opening of the slits. Therefore, among the strain measures of the discrete assembly, we have to add (c) the opening of a slit, which is measured by the relative microdisplacement between two slits \mathcal{H} and \mathcal{K} , with centres H and K , respectively, interacting through the point $J \equiv J^h \equiv J^k$, represented by the vector $\mathbf{d}_j = \mathbf{u}_d^h - \mathbf{u}_d^k$; (d) the relative total displacement between an \mathcal{A} particle and an \mathcal{H} slit, interacting through point $Q \equiv Q^a \equiv Q^h$, represented by vector $\mathbf{u}_q^{ah} = \mathbf{u}^a + \mathbf{W}^a(Q - A) + \mathbf{u}_d^a - [\mathbf{u}^h + \mathbf{W}^h(Q - H) + \mathbf{u}_d^h]$.

Figure 3: Sketch of interactions between grains, slits and grain/slit.

The generalized forces associated with the kinematic quantities listed above are: (a) the force and (b) the couple between \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} , represented by a vector \mathbf{t}_p and a skew-symmetric tensor \mathbf{C}_p , respectively, acting at the contact point P ; (c) the opening force between \mathcal{H} and \mathcal{K} slits, represented by the vector \mathbf{z}_j accounting for slit interaction, acting at the contact point J ; (d) the particle-slit interaction force, represented by vector \mathbf{r}_q , acting at the contact point Q (Figure 3).

Considering a small periodic neighbourhood of the discrete system \mathcal{M} , called 'module', which must be large enough to be representative of the given system and sufficiently small to take advantage of the localization theorem, the mean virtual work of the contact actions over \mathcal{M} can be written as

$$\pi^i = \frac{1}{V} \left\{ \sum_p [\mathbf{t}_p \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_p + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{C}_p \cdot \check{\mathbf{W}}_p] + \sum_j \mathbf{z}_j \cdot \check{\mathbf{d}}_j + \sum_q \mathbf{r}_q \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_q^{ah} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where V is the volume of the module and the summation is extended to all the contact points between the elements of \mathcal{M} . From now on, the symbol \sim stands for any field.

According to the discrete-continuum coarse-graining approaches [54, 55], we introduce a kinematical map relating discrete-to-continuous kinematical fields given by Taylor expansions up to the first order of the vector fields $\mathbf{u}(X)$ and of the skew-symmetric tensor field $\mathbf{W}(X)$, and up to the second order for the vector field $\mathbf{u}_d(X)$

$$\mathbf{u}^a = \mathbf{u}(X) + \nabla \mathbf{u}(X)(A - X) \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{W}^a = \mathbf{W}(X) + \nabla \mathbf{W}(X)(A - X) \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_d^h = \mathbf{u}_d(X) + \nabla \mathbf{u}_d(X)(H - X) + \frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_d(X)(H - X)(H - X) \quad (8)$$

where X is the centre of the module. This map requires that the lattice system undergoes continuous deformations and is a generalization of the so-called Cauchy-Born map used in crystal elasticity. Assuming that a continuous neighbourhood of X occupies the same Euclidean region of the module, the continuum equivalent to this discrete system can be obtained by requiring that the mean work of the contact actions of the module (5) equals the work density of the stresses, acting on the neighbourhood of the continuum, for any admissible kinematical field.

On assuming the kinematical maps represented by equations (6)-(8), the strain measures can be written as:

$$\mathbf{u}_p = (\nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{W})(A - B) + \nabla \mathbf{W}[(P - A) \otimes (A - X) - (P - B) \otimes (B - X)] \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{W}_p = \nabla \mathbf{W}(A - B) \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{d}_j = \nabla \mathbf{u}_d(H - K) + \frac{1}{2} \nabla \mathbf{u}_d^2[(H - X) \otimes (H - X) - (K - X) \otimes (K - X)] \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_q^{ah} = (\nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{W})(A - H) + \nabla \mathbf{W}[(Q - A) \otimes (A - X) - (Q - H) \otimes (H - X)] + \nabla \mathbf{u}_d(A - H) + \frac{1}{2} \nabla \mathbf{u}_d^2[(A - X) \otimes (A - X) - (H - X) \otimes (H - X)] \quad (12)$$

where the explicit dependence of the fields on X was dropped. Using the defined strain measures, the mean internal work (Equation (5)) of the contact actions over the module \mathcal{M} can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi^i &= \frac{1}{V} [\sum_p \mathbf{t}_p \otimes (A - B) + \sum_q \mathbf{r}_q \otimes (A - H)] \cdot (\nabla \check{\mathbf{u}} - \check{\mathbf{W}}) + \\
&+ \frac{1}{2V} \sum_p \{2\mathbf{t}_p \otimes [(P - A) \otimes (A - X) - (P - B) \otimes (B - X)] + \mathbf{C}_p \otimes (A - B) + \\
&\quad \sum_q 2\mathbf{r}_q \otimes [(Q - A) \otimes (A - X) - (Q - H) \otimes (H - X)]\} \cdot \nabla \check{\mathbf{W}} + \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{V} [\sum_j \mathbf{z}_j \otimes (H - K) + \sum_q \mathbf{r}_q \otimes (A - H)] \cdot \nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d + \\
&+ \frac{1}{2V} \{ \sum_j \mathbf{z}_j \otimes [(H - X) \otimes (H - X) - (K - X) \otimes (K - X)] + \\
&\quad \sum_q \mathbf{r}_q \otimes [(A - X) \otimes (A - X) - (H - X) \otimes (H - X)] \} \cdot \nabla^2 \check{\mathbf{u}}_d \quad (13)
\end{aligned}$$

and, by reordering the terms:

$$\pi^i = \mathbf{S} \cdot (\nabla \check{\mathbf{u}} - \check{\mathbf{W}}) + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{S} \cdot \nabla \check{\mathbf{W}} + \mathbf{z} \cdot \nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{Z} \cdot \nabla^2 \check{\mathbf{u}}_d \quad (14)$$

with:

$$\mathbf{S} = \frac{1}{V} [\sum_p \mathbf{t}_p \otimes (A - B) + \sum_q \mathbf{r}_q \otimes (A - H)] \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{S} &= \frac{1}{V} \{ \sum_p 2\mathbf{t}_p \otimes [(P - A) \otimes (A - X) - (P - B) \otimes (B - X)] + \mathbf{C}_p \otimes (A - B) + \\
&\quad + \sum_q 2\mathbf{r}_q \otimes [(Q - A) \otimes (A - X) - (Q - H) \otimes (H - X)] \} \quad (16)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{z} = \frac{1}{V} [\sum_j \mathbf{z}_j \otimes (H - K) + \sum_q \mathbf{r}_q \otimes (A - H)] \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{Z} &= \frac{1}{V} \{ \sum_j \mathbf{z}_j \otimes [(H - X) \otimes (H - X) - (K - X) \otimes (K - X)] + \\
&\quad \sum_q \mathbf{r}_q \otimes [(A - X) \otimes (A - X) - (H - X) \otimes (H - X)] \}. \quad (18)
\end{aligned}$$

Considering a continuous neighbourhood of X which occupies the same region of the module \mathcal{M} , we can then recognize that the fields $(\nabla \check{\mathbf{u}} - \check{\mathbf{W}})$, $\nabla \check{\mathbf{W}}$, $\nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d$ and $\nabla^2 \check{\mathbf{u}}_d$ represent the linearized strain measures of the multi-field continuum defined above. Resorting to the localization theorem and requiring that the mean work (Equation (14)) equals the internal work density of this continuum for any value of the corresponding strain fields, the equivalent continuum contact actions are identified as the work-conjugated fields in the formula (14). Equations (15) to (18) then provide the second-order stress tensor \mathbf{S} , the third-order couple-stress tensor \mathbf{S} , the second-order microstress tensor \mathbf{z} , and the third-order hyperstress tensor \mathbf{Z} of the equivalent continuum as a function of contact actions between particles, and of

the slit-slit and slit-particle interactions, independently of the choice of the related response functions.

Now, let us assume that the response functions of the contact actions of the module are linearly elastic, that is: $\mathbf{t}_p = \mathbf{K}_p \mathbf{u}_p$, $\mathbf{C}_p = \mathbb{K}_p \mathbf{W}_p$, $\mathbf{z}_j = \mathbf{T}_j \mathbf{d}_j$, $\mathbf{r}_q = \mathbb{R}_q \mathbf{u}_q^{ah}$ where \mathbf{K}_p is the stiffness tensor tied to the matrix elasticity, \mathbb{K}_p is the related rotation stiffness tensor, \mathbf{T}_j is the stiffness tensor of a slit, and \mathbb{R}_q is the interaction tensor between a slit and a particle. Applying the maps (6)-(8) between discrete and continuum fields to the actual kinematical descriptors, we can obtain the constitutive relationships of the equivalent multifield continuum. These are reported in Appendix A. After some algebra, the stress-strain relations of the multifield continuum can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{S} &= \mathbb{A}(\nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{W}) + \mathbb{B} \nabla \mathbf{W} + \mathbb{C} \nabla \mathbf{u}_d + \mathbb{D} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_d \\
\mathbf{S} &= \mathbb{E}(\nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{W}) + \mathbb{F} \nabla \mathbf{W} + \mathbb{G} \nabla \mathbf{u}_d + \mathbb{H} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_d \\
\mathbf{z} &= \mathbb{I}(\nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{W}) + \mathbb{L} \nabla \mathbf{W} + \mathbb{M} \nabla \mathbf{u}_d + \mathbb{N} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_d \\
\mathbf{Z} &= \mathbb{O}(\nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{W}) + \mathbb{P} \nabla \mathbf{W} + \mathbb{Q} \nabla \mathbf{u}_d + \mathbb{R} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_d
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

The constitutive tensors of fourth ($\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{C}, \mathbb{I}, \mathbb{M}$), fifth ($\mathbb{B}, \mathbb{D}, \mathbb{E}, \mathbb{G}, \mathbb{L}, \mathbb{N}, \mathbb{O}, \mathbb{Q}$) and sixth ($\mathbb{F}, \mathbb{H}, \mathbb{P}, \mathbb{R}$) order have components which depend on size, shape, arrangement, and orientation of the internal phases as well as on the elastic constants of the matrix. Moreover, if the discrete continuum is hyperelastic, also the equivalent continuum is hyperelastic, and the constitutive tensor satisfy symmetry relations, which are: $\mathbb{C} \mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{U} = \mathbf{U} \cdot \mathbb{I} \mathbf{V}$ for all the second-order tensors \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} ; $\mathbb{B} \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbb{E} \mathbf{V}$, $\mathbb{D} \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbb{O} \mathbf{V}$ and $\mathbb{L} \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbb{O} \mathbf{V}$ for all the third-order \mathbf{T} and second-order tensors \mathbf{V} ; $\mathbb{N} \mathbf{Y} \cdot \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{Y} \cdot \mathbb{Q} \mathbf{V}$ for all the fourth-order \mathbf{Y} and second-order tensors \mathbf{V} .

Let us now consider a constrained lattice model in which the particle rotations are assumed constant in the module (Voigt's hypothesis [53]), so that:

$$\mathbf{W}^a = \mathbf{W}(X) = \frac{1}{2}[\nabla \mathbf{u}(X) - \nabla \mathbf{u}(X)^T] \tag{20}$$

and particles and slits are in contact. In this rotation-constrained model, the strain measures are: $\mathbf{u}_p = \mathbf{E}(A - B)$, with $\mathbf{E} = (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)/2$, which is the

symmetric part of the gradient of displacements, and the relative microdisplacement field \mathbf{d} , which contains the first and second gradient of microdisplacement (11). In this case, the work density is reduced to:

$$\pi^i = \frac{1}{V}(\mathbf{S} \cdot \check{\mathbf{E}} + \mathbf{z} \cdot \nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d + \mathbf{Z} \cdot \nabla^2 \check{\mathbf{u}}_d), \quad (21)$$

and the stress-strain relations of the continuum are:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{S} &= \mathbb{A}\mathbf{E} + \mathbb{C}\nabla\mathbf{u}_d + \mathbb{D}\nabla^2\mathbf{u}_d & \mathbf{z} &= \mathbb{I}\mathbf{E} + \mathbb{M}\nabla\mathbf{u}_d + \mathbb{N}\nabla^2\mathbf{u}_d \\ \mathbf{Z} &= \mathbb{O}\mathbf{E} + \mathbb{Q}\nabla\mathbf{u}_d + \mathbb{R}\nabla^2\mathbf{u}_d. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The expressions by components of these elastic tensors are reported in Appendix B.

4. The microcracked continuum equivalent to a discrete lattice: derivation of field equations

Let us now consider a reference volume Ω of the microcracked continuum with a regular boundary $\partial\Omega$ and outward unit normal \mathbf{n} . Starting from the internal work of this continuum:

$$\pi^i = \int_{\Omega} (\mathbf{S} \cdot \check{\mathbf{E}} + \mathbf{z} \cdot \nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d + \mathbf{Z} \cdot \nabla^2 \check{\mathbf{u}}_d) dV \quad (23)$$

and applying the theorem of divergence to the last term, the work of the hyperstress, we obtain:

$$\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{Z} \cdot \nabla^2 \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dV = - \int_{\Omega} \text{div} \mathbf{Z} \cdot \nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dV + \int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dS. \quad (24)$$

The internal work can be rewritten as follows:

$$\pi^i = \int_{\Omega} [\mathbf{S} \cdot \check{\mathbf{E}} + (\mathbf{z} - \text{div} \mathbf{Z}) \cdot \nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d] dV + \int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{Z} \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dS. \quad (25)$$

The theorem of divergence can be applied to the second term of (25), obtaining:

$$\int_{\Omega} (\mathbf{z} - \text{div}\mathbf{Z}) \cdot \nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dV = - \int_{\Omega} \text{div}(\mathbf{z} - \text{div}\mathbf{Z}) \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_d + \int_{\partial\Omega} (\mathbf{z} - \text{div}\mathbf{Z})\mathbf{n} \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dS, \quad (26)$$

while the gradient of microdisplacement in the third term of (25) can be resolved into its surface and normal-to-the surface components $\nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d = \nabla_s \check{\mathbf{u}}_d + \nabla_{\mathbf{n}} \check{\mathbf{u}}_d$ with $\nabla_s \check{\mathbf{u}}_d = \nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n})$ and $\nabla_{\mathbf{n}} \check{\mathbf{u}}_d = \partial_{\mathbf{n}} \check{\mathbf{u}}_d \mathbf{n}$, with \mathbf{I} identity tensor. The last term of (25) can then be rewritten as:

$$\int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dS = \int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla_s \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dS + \int_{\partial\Omega} (\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n})\mathbf{n} \cdot \partial_{\mathbf{n}} \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dS. \quad (27)$$

The theorem of divergence can be applied to these terms in several ways [61, 62, 63]. Here, we follow the procedure described in the last reference, which accounts for the presence of contact actions distributed along lines $\partial(\partial\Omega)$ and write:

$$\int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla_s \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dS = - \int_{\partial\Omega} \text{div}_s(\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n})\mathbf{n} \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dS + \int_{\partial(\partial\Omega)} (\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n})\mathbf{m} \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dL. \quad (28)$$

where \mathbf{m} is a unit vector orthogonal to both \mathbf{n} and the tangent direction of $\partial(\partial\Omega)$ and pointing outward from the interior of $\partial\Omega$. It should be noticed that at an edge $\widehat{\partial\Omega}$, \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{m} are not univocally defined. In accordance with [63], it is assumed that

$$\int_{\partial(\partial\Omega)} (\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n})\mathbf{m} \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dL = \int_{\widehat{\partial\Omega}} \llbracket \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n} \rrbracket \mathbf{m} \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dL \quad (29)$$

where $\llbracket \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n} \rrbracket$ denotes the edge average of $\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n}$ over the tangent \mathbf{m}' , \mathbf{m}'' and the normal vectors \mathbf{n}' , \mathbf{n}'' of the two surfaces connecting at $\widehat{\partial\Omega}$, which is $\llbracket \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n} \rrbracket = (\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n}')\mathbf{m}' + (\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n}'')\mathbf{m}''$.

In conclusion, the work of the internal actions acting on the multifield continuum can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi^i = & - \int_{\Omega} \text{div} \mathbf{S} \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}} dV + \int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{S}\mathbf{n} \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}} dS + \quad (30) \\ & - \int_{\Omega} \text{div}(\mathbf{z} - \text{div}\mathbf{Z}) \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dV + \int_{\partial\Omega} [(\mathbf{z} - \text{div}\mathbf{Z})\mathbf{n} - \text{div}_s(\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n})] \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dS + \\ & + \int_{\partial\Omega} (\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n})\mathbf{n} \cdot \partial_{\mathbf{n}} \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dS + \int_{\widehat{\partial\Omega}} \llbracket \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n} \rrbracket \mathbf{m} \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dL. \end{aligned}$$

The external work of the external forces acting on the multified continuum can be written as:

$$\pi^o = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{b} \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{c} \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dV + \int_{\partial\Omega} (\mathbf{f} \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{g} \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_d + \mathbf{h} \cdot \partial_{\mathbf{n}} \check{\mathbf{u}}_d) dS + \int_{\widehat{\partial\Omega}} \mathbf{h}_L \cdot \check{\mathbf{u}}_d dL \quad (31)$$

where \mathbf{b} is the external body force and \mathbf{f} the surface traction acting on the macrostructure (matrix), \mathbf{c} is the body force acting on the microstructure represented by the microcracks, \mathbf{g} and \mathbf{h} are the surface traction and hypertraction acting on the microstructure surface boundary, and \mathbf{h}_L is the concentrated force acting on $\widehat{\partial\Omega}$. The following balance equations are obtained

$$\operatorname{div} \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{0} \quad \operatorname{div} (\mathbf{z} - \operatorname{div} \mathbf{Z}) + \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{on } \Omega \quad (32)$$

together with the boundary conditions on $\partial\Omega$:

$$\mathbf{S} \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{f} \quad (33)$$

$$(\mathbf{z} - \operatorname{div} \mathbf{Z}) \mathbf{n} - \operatorname{div}_s (\mathbf{Z} \mathbf{n}) = \mathbf{g}$$

$$(\mathbf{Z} \mathbf{n}) \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{h} \quad (34)$$

and on the edge $\widehat{\partial\Omega}$:

$$[[\mathbf{Z} \mathbf{n}]] \mathbf{m} = \mathbf{h}_L. \quad (35)$$

5. Microcracked onedimensional bar

We consider here a sample problem concerning a one-dimensional bar with constrained microrotations, whose sketch is reported in Figure 4. Given that the longitudinal components of the macro and micro displacement fields are called, respectively, u and u_d , the constitutive relations for the stress measures are

$$S = \mathbb{A}u' + \mathbb{C}u'_d + \mathbb{D}u''_d, \quad z = \mathbb{I}u' + \mathbb{M}u'_d + \mathbb{N}u''_d \quad Z = \mathbb{O}u' + \mathbb{Q}u'_d + \mathbb{R}u''_d \quad (36)$$

Figure 4: Sketch of the one-dimensional microcracked bar.

where the symbol $'$ stands for derivative according to the longitudinal coordinate of the bar x . $\mathbb{A}, \mathbb{C}, \mathbb{D}, \mathbb{I}, \mathbb{M}, \mathbb{N}, \mathbb{O}, \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R}$ are the material constitutive constants which can be calculated using the expressions reported in Appendix B.

Let us consider a microcracked bar of length L clamped on the left-hand side and subjected to a tensile force F on the right-hand side. When a tensile force is applied, slits open and give rise to a microdisplacement field which adds up to the macrodisplacement, so that the total displacement $u_{tot} = u + u_d$ is greater than that of the pristine uncracked bar u_0 . Such a behaviour can be seen as an effect introduced by an applied microforce (microactions) or as a consequence of the reduction of the global stiffness. Here, the first point of view is assumed.

5.1. Static response in the absence of particle-slit interactions

If slits are arranged as in Figure 4 and the interaction between particles and slits is ignored, the tensors $\mathbb{C}, \mathbb{D}, \mathbb{I}, \mathbb{M}$, as well as $\mathbb{O}, \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R}$ are null. The Navier equations can be obtained by substituting the constitutive equations (36) into the balance equations (32). In the absence of body forces and of particle-slit interactions, the two decoupled balance equations can be written as:

$$\mathbb{A}u'' = 0, \quad \mathbb{M}u_d'' = 0. \quad (37)$$

Since $Z = 0$, only the following macro- and micro- boundary conditions have to be enforced:

$$u(0) = 0 \quad S(L) = \sigma \quad (38)$$

$$u_d(0) = 0 \quad z(L) = \lambda\sigma \quad (39)$$

where $\sigma = F/A$, with A area of the bar cross-section. The microforce z is assumed to depend linearly on the applied macroforce F through a constant λ , which, in its turn, depends on the interaction between macro and microstructure.

The field equations (37) together with the boundary conditions (38)-(39) have a solution that can be written in closed form as:

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{\mathbb{A}} \sigma x \quad u_d(x) = \frac{\lambda}{\mathbb{M}} \sigma x, \quad (40)$$

which shows that the total displacement, for the assumed slit distribution, is a linear function. Based on the formulae of Appendix B, for the considered system, it is obtained that $\mathbb{A} = E$ with E Young's modulus, and $\mathbb{M} = EA_c l/l_c^2$ where l is the size of the module, A_c is the area of the microcracked cross-section, and l_c is the microcrack longitudinal size (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Sketch of the interactions particle/particle a) slit/slit b) particle/slit c).

Figure 6a reports a nondimensional diagram of the total axial displacement field of the bar for three different values of the nondimensional crack density $\rho_c = l_c/l$, assuming $\lambda = 1$. The axial displacements of Figure 6 are made nondimensional by dividing them by the displacement of the tip of

the uncracked bar $u_0(L)$. Figure 6a shows that longitudinal displacements increase linearly from the clamped end to the free end, where a force is applied, and shows as well that they increase when the crack density $\rho = l_c/l$ increases. It should be noted that, since we are ignoring the interaction between particles and slits, the u field does not change by increasing the slit density, which, on the contrary, remarkably affects the microdisplacement field u_d . This is shown in Figure 6b, which reports the normalized microdisplacements for increasing ρ_c .

Figure 6: In the absence of particle/slit interaction: a) total displacement field of the microcracked bar normalized to the tip displacement. Dots are results from the finite element model. b) Microdisplacement field of the microcracked bar normalized to the tip displacement.

5.2. Static response in the presence of particle-slit interactions

In the presence of particle-slit interactions, the tensors $\mathbb{C}, \mathbb{D}, \mathbb{I}, \mathbb{N}, \mathbb{O}, \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R}$ are not null, and the Navier equations are coupled, as it results substituting the constitutive equations (36) into the balance equations (32). In the absence of body forces they can be written as:

$$\mathbb{A}u'' + \mathbb{C}u_d'' + \mathbb{D}u_d''' = 0 \quad (41)$$

$$\mathbb{I}u'' + \mathbb{M}u_d'' - \mathbb{O}u_d''' + (\mathbb{N} - \mathbb{Q})u_d''' - \mathbb{R}u_d'''' = 0, \quad (42)$$

which must hold together with the following boundary conditions:

$$u(0) = 0 \quad S(L) = \sigma \quad (43)$$

$$u_d(0) = 0 \quad z(L) - \text{div}Z(L) = \lambda_1\sigma \quad (44)$$

$$u_d'(0) = 0 \quad Z(L) = \lambda_2\sigma. \quad (45)$$

In this case, given the onedimensional nature of the continuum, the boundary conditions on the edge $\widehat{\partial\Omega}$ cannot be defined. As a consequence, the order of the differential equations is limited to three, and it must be assumed that $\mathbb{R} = 0$. Moreover, based on the results reported in Appendix B, the constitutive constants assume the following values $\mathbb{A} = E + \alpha E$, $\mathbb{C} = \mathbb{I} = \alpha E$, $\mathbb{D} = \mathbb{O} = \alpha El$, $\mathbb{M} = \alpha E + EA_c l / l_c^2$, $\mathbb{N} = \mathbb{Q} = \alpha El + EA_c l^2 / l_c^2$, where for the slit-particle interaction a linear relationship is assumed, measured by the coefficient α .

To elucidate the effect of the particle-slit interaction, we first display the response of a model where the second-order effects are neglected ($\mathbb{D} = \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{O} = \mathbb{Q} = 0$). In this case, the static displacement fields have a linear form that is:

$$u(x) = \frac{\mathbb{C} - \mathbb{M}}{\mathbb{C}\mathbb{I} - \mathbb{A}\mathbb{M}} \sigma x \quad u_d(x) = \lambda_1 \frac{\mathbb{I} - \mathbb{A}}{\mathbb{C}\mathbb{I} - \mathbb{A}\mathbb{M}} \sigma x \quad (46)$$

which shows that the u displacement is influenced by the particle-slit interaction and increases as the slit density increases (\mathbb{M} decreases). This is shown in Figure 7 a, which reports the normalized increase of the macrodisplacement in relation to the displacement of the uncracked bar $(u - u_0)/u_0$, which increases as the slit density increases. The displacement u_d increases as well for increasing slit density, as shown in Figure 7 b. Figure 8 reports the normalized total displacement field obtained assuming $\alpha = 0.02$ and $\lambda_1 = 1$ for different slit densities and shows that, considering particle/slit interaction, the match of the proposed model with the finite element model remarkably improves. The comparison between Figure 8 and 6a also shows that, on the whole, the equivalent model with interaction is stiffer than when particle-slit interaction is ignored.

Considering also second-order effects provides with a solution which is no longer linear, but contains a linear combination of linear and exponential terms, although the linear part prevails. Also in this case both the u and u_d displacements increase as the slit density increases, with results which are very similar to those obtained when neglecting second-order effects. This is shown in Figure 9 which reports the normalized total displacement field obtained assuming $\lambda_2 = 0.01$ for different slit densities.

6. Comparison with finite-element models

In order to investigate the capability of the multi-field model to effectively represent the behavior of a microcracked material, in this Section, we

Figure 7: In the presence of particle/slit interaction: a) normalized increase of the macrodisplacement and b) normalized microdisplacement for different slit densities.

Figure 8: In the presence of particle/slit interaction: normalized total displacement field of the microcracked bar. Dots represent results from a finite element model.

compared the results obtained from a finite-element (FE) model to those of the equivalent model. The numerical FE solution was obtained using the software ANSYS. The FE model consists of a linear elastic plane-strain 2D plate with holes with varying density. The plate consists on a rectangular domain of height $h=0.1$ m and length $L=1$ m, and has a cross-section area $A=0.1$ m². All the displacements of the nodes on the left-hand boundary of the plate are restrained, while a tensile force $F=1$ N, giving rise to a pressure of $\sigma=1/0.1$ N/m² is applied on the right-hand side. All the nodes were constrained not to move in the y direction to mimic the one-dimensional model scheme. Free-stress conditions are applied on the upper and lower boundaries. The Young's modulus is $E=48 \cdot 10^5$ kN/cm². Different sizes and densities of voids are investigated: circular holes of area A_s and

Figure 9: In the presence of second-order particle/slit interaction: normalized total displacement field of the microcracked bar. Dots represent results from a finite element model.

diameter l_c (see Figure 4), periodically spaced at a distance l are considered, resulting into different values of $\rho_c = A_s/(lh) = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3$. The model mesh is displayed in Figure 10. The results of the finite element model (dots) are compared to those of the microcracked equivalent bar (continuous lines) in Figures 6, 8 and 9 showing a very good match of the two models when the particle/slit interaction is taken into consideration.

Figure 10: FE model with different void densities

7. Conclusions

This paper illustrates how to derive a multifield continuum model equivalent, in terms of virtual work, to a discrete periodic assembly made of rigid particles embedded in a deformable matrix which also contains voids, pores or cracks. The displacement fields chosen for the kinematic description of the discrete assembly includes the standard displacement of the particles, their microrotations, and the microdisplacement of the slits. The equivalence in terms of virtual works between the micro and macro model is used to identify the constitutive relationships of the continuum equivalent to the discrete periodic system with assigned deformations and internal constraints, obtaining constitutive relationships as a function of the contact actions. Bulk and surface balance equations of the equivalent continuum are also derived within the general framework of work equivalence between internal and external actions. In this paper the equivalence procedure is applied to the linear case with constrained microrotation, nevertheless, it is completely general and applies also to nonlinear constitutive relationships of contact actions. The continuum obtained is an implicit non-local continuum whose strain measures include the first gradient of macrodisplacements and microrotations and the second-gradient of microdisplacements. This was done to include nonlocal effects in the description of the interaction between slits and particle/slits, and further enables the overcoming of typical drawbacks of classical local models, which do not retain memory of the internal length scale, neither reveal the dispersive character of propagating waves, and result, in many cases (e.g. [20]), in the ill-positioning of field equations and related mesh-dependence of finite element models formulations. The ability to describe these physical aspect paves the way to more refined interpretations of the response obtained from nondestructive ultrasonic tests and to the identification of material properties such as porosity or smeared damage. The results obtained from the equivalent model in the absence and in the presence of particle/slit interactions were compared to those of a finite element model, showing a very good match between the static responses of the finite element model and the equivalent model accounting for particle/slit interactions, with the displacement microfield increasing with increasing porosity.

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9. Appendix A

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{S} = & \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_p \{ \mathbf{K}_p [(\nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{W})(A - B) + \nabla \mathbf{W}[(P - A) \otimes (A - X)] - (P - B) \otimes (B - X)] \} \right. \\
& \otimes (A - B) + \sum_q \mathbb{R}_q \{ (\nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{W})(A - H) + \nabla \mathbf{W}[(Q - A) \otimes (A - X) - \\
& -(Q - B)] \otimes (B - X) + \nabla \mathbf{u}_d(A - H) + \frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_d [(A - X) \otimes (A - X) - \\
& \left. -(H - X) \otimes (H - X)] \otimes (A - H) \} \right) \quad (47)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{S} = & \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_p \{ 2\mathbf{K}_p (\nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{W})(A - B) \otimes [(P - A) \otimes (A - X) - (P - B) \otimes (B - X)] + \right. \\
& \left. + \mathbb{K}_p \nabla \mathbf{W}(A - B) \otimes (A - B) \} + \sum_q \{ 2\mathbb{R}_q (\nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{W})(A - H) + \nabla \mathbf{W}[(Q - A) \otimes (A - X) - \right. \\
& \left. -(Q - H)] \otimes (H - X) + \nabla \mathbf{u}_d(A - H) + \frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_d [(A - X) \otimes (A - X) - \right. \\
& \left. -(H - X) \otimes (H - X)] \} \otimes [(Q - A) \otimes (A - X) - (Q - H) \otimes (H - X)] \right) \quad (48)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{z} = & \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_q \mathbb{R}_q \{ (\nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{W})(A - H) + \nabla \mathbf{W}[(Q - A) \otimes (A - X)] - (Q - B) \otimes (B - X) \} + \right. \\
& \left. + \nabla \mathbf{u}_d(A - H) + \frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_d [(A - X) \otimes (A - X) - (H - X) \otimes (H - X)] \} \otimes (A - H) \right) + \\
& \sum_j \mathbf{T}_j \{ \nabla \mathbf{u}_d(H - K) + \frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_d [(H - X) \otimes (H - X) - (K - X) \otimes (K - X)] \} \otimes (H - K) \quad (49)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{Z} = & \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_q \mathbb{R}_q \{ (\nabla \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{W})(A - H) + \nabla \mathbf{W} [(Q - A) \otimes (A - X)] - (Q - B) \otimes (B - X) \} + \right. \\
& + \nabla \mathbf{u}_d (A - H) + \frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_d [(A - X) \otimes (A - X) - (H - X) \otimes (H - X)] \} \\
& \otimes [(A - X) \otimes (A - X) - (H - X) \otimes (H - X)] + \sum_j \mathbf{T}_j \{ \nabla \mathbf{u}_d (H - K) + \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_d [(H - X) \otimes (H - X) - (K - X) \otimes (K - X)] \} \\
& \left. \otimes [(H - X) \otimes (H - X) - (K - X) \otimes (K - X)] \right) \tag{50}
\end{aligned}$$

10. Appendix B

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{A}_{ijhk} &= \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_p K_{p ih} (A - B)_j (A - B)_k + \sum_q \mathbb{R}_{q ih} (A - H)_j (A - H)_k \right) \\
\mathbb{B}_{ijhkl} &= \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_p K_{p ih} [(P - A)_k (A - X)_l - (P - B)_k (B - X)_l] (A - B)_j + \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \sum_q \mathbb{R}_{q ih} [(Q - A)_k (A - X)_l - (Q - B)_k (B - X)_l] (A - H)_j \right) \\
\mathbb{C}_{ijhk} &= \frac{1}{V} \sum_q \mathbb{R}_{q ih} (A - H)_j (A - H)_k \\
\mathbb{D}_{ijhkl} &= \frac{1}{2V} \sum_q \mathbb{R}_{q ih} [(A - X)_k (A - X)_l - (H - X)_k (H - X)_l] (A - H)_j
\end{aligned} \tag{51}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}_{ijhkl} &= \frac{2}{V} \left(\sum_p K_{pik} [(P-A)_j(A-X)_k - (P-B)_j(B-X)_k] (A-B)_l + \right. \\
&\quad \left. \sum_q \mathbb{R}_{qik} [(Q-A)_j(A-X)_k - (A-H)_j(Q-H)_k] (A-H)_l \right) \\
\mathbb{F}_{ijhklm} &= \frac{2}{V} \left(\sum_p \{ K_{pih} [(P-A)_l(A-X)_m - (P-B)_l(B-X)_m] \right. \\
&\quad [(P-A)_j(A-X)_h - (P-B)_j(B-X)_h] + \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{K}_{ijkl} (A-B)_h (A-B)_m \} \\
&\quad \left. \sum_q \mathbb{R}_{qih} [(Q-A)_l(A-X)_m - (Q-H)_l(H-X)_m] \right. \\
&\quad \left. [(Q-A)_j(A-H)_h - (Q-H)_j(H-X)_h] \right) \\
\mathbb{G}_{ijhkl} &= \frac{2}{V} \sum_p \mathbb{R}_{pik} [(Q-A)_j(A-X)_k - (Q-H)_j(H-X)_k] (A-H)_l \\
\mathbb{H}_{ijhklm} &= \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_q \mathbb{R}_{jih} [(A-X)_l(A-X)_m - (H-X)_l(H-X)_m] \right. \\
&\quad \left. [(Q-A)_j(A-H)_h - (Q-H)_j(H-X)_h] \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{52}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{I}_{ijhk} &= \frac{1}{V} \sum_q \mathbb{R}_{qih} (A - H)_j (A - H)_k \\
\mathbb{L}_{ijkl} &= \frac{1}{V} \sum_q \mathbb{R}_{qih} [(Q - A)_k (A - X)_l - (Q - B)_k (B - X)_l] (A - H)_j \\
\mathbb{M}_{ijkh} &= \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_j T_{jih} (H - K)_j (H - K)_k + \sum_q \mathbb{R}_{qih} (A - H)_j (A - H)_k \right) \\
\mathbb{N}_{ijhkl} &= \frac{1}{2V} \left(\sum_j T_{jih} [(H - X)_k (H - X)_l - (K - X)_k (K - X)_l] (H - K)_j + \right. \\
&\quad \left. \sum_q \mathbb{R}_{qih} [(A - X)_k (A - X)_l - (H - X)_k (H - X)_l] (A - H)_j \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{53}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{O}_{ijhkl} &= \frac{1}{V} \sum_q \mathbb{R}_{pik} [(Q - A)_j (A - X)_k - (Q - H)_j (H - X)_k] (A - H)_l \\
\mathbb{P}_{ijhklm} &= \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_q \mathbb{R}_{qih} [(Q - A)_l (A - X)_m - (Q - H)_l (H - X)_m] \right. \\
&\quad \left. [(Q - A)_j (A - H)_h - (Q - H)_j (H - X)_h] \right) \\
\mathbb{Q}_{ijhkl} &= \frac{1}{V} \left(\sum_q \mathbb{R}_{qik} [(A - X)_j (A - X)_k - (H - X)_j (H - X)_k] (A - H)_l + \right. \\
&\quad \left. \sum_j T_{jik} [(H - X)_j (H - X)_k - (K - X)_j (K - X)_k] (H - K)_l \right) \\
\mathbb{R}_{ijhklm} &= \frac{1}{2V} \left(\sum_q \mathbb{R}_{qih} [(A - X)_l (A - X)_m - (H - X)_l (H - X)_m] \right. \\
&\quad [(A - X)_j (A - X)_h - (H - X)_j (H - X)_h] + \\
&\quad \left. \sum_j T_{jih} [(H - X)_l (H - X)_m - (K - X)_l (K - X)_m] \right. \\
&\quad \left. [(H - X)_j (H - X)_h - (K - X)_j (K - X)_h] \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{54}$$

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